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“ASSOCIATION BETWEEN BODY MASS INDEX AND HYPERTENSION IN A VIEW TO PREPARE INFORMATION BOOKLET ON PREVENTION OF COMPLICATIONS AMONG HYPERTENSIVE PATIENTS”

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Hypertension has become a systemic disease with more incidence and prevalence rate among the modern generation. Dietary and lifestyle changes can lower blood pressure and decrease the risk of health complications, although treatment with medication is still often necessary in people for whom lifestyle changes are not enough or not effective. Dietary and lifestyle changes can improve blood pressure control and decrease the risk of health complications, although drug treatment is still often necessary in people for whom lifestyle changes are not enough or not effective. A number of important contributory factors for hypertension have been identified, including overweight/obesity, excessive dietary sodium intake, low physical activity, smoking, and high alcohol intake. Previous studies have shown that being overweight or obese is associated with a higher risk for hypertension. Hypertension, a condition developed as a result of high blood pressure and is strongly correlated with Body Mass Index. Obesity was noted to be a single best predictor of hypertension incidence, and was regarded as a major controllable contributor to hypertension. Overweight and obesity is conveniently determined from Body Mass Index. **Research Methodology:** The study was conducted among hypertensive patients, for assessing the association between Body Mass Index and Hypertension. At first a rapport was established with the patients and the purpose of the study was explained to them. The sample of 100 was selected by using non-probability convenient sampling technique. On the first day of data collection, the investigator introduced him and explained the nature, purpose of the study to the clients. Verbal and written Consent was obtained to participate in the study and confidentiality of their responses was assured. Hypertensive patients were identified and their blood pressure, height, weight and abdominal girth were

collected. Demographic variables and clinical variables were collected using demographic variable proforma and clinical variable proforma. Body Mass Index was calculated according to the universally accepted formula.

Result: On analyzing data, a strong association between Body Mass Index and Hypertension was found. Regarding socio demographic variables there was association between Age, sex, occupational status and marital status with hypertension. Whereas, no association was there for educational level, residing place, family income and type of family with Hypertension. Regarding Clinical variables, there was association between Type of food and Frequency of meal with hypertension. Whereas no association was found for Co morbid illness and Common cooking methods with Hypertension. **Conclusion:** The study revealed that there is association between age, sex, occupational status and marital status with hypertension whereas, no association was found for educational level, residing place, family income and type of family with Hypertension. On analyzing data, we can deduce that 42% of the sample were overweight 52% were of normal weight and 6% were underweight. There is significant association between Systolic blood pressure and Body Mass Index. There is significant association between

Diastolic blood pressure and Body Mass Index. Hence the researcher concluded that there is an association between Body Mass Index and Hypertension.

Keywords: H: Hypothesis, df: Degree of freedom

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Globally, high blood pressure is estimated to cause 7.1 million deaths, about 13% of the total, according to world health organization. About 62% of cerebrovascular disease and 49% of ischemic heart disease are attributable to suboptimal blood pressure. Overweight and obesity increases the risk of high blood pressure, coronary heart disease, ischemic stroke, Type II diabetes mellitus and certain cancers. Worldwide about 58% of diabetes mellitus and 21% of ischemic heart disease are attributable to Body Mass Index over 21 kg/ meter square. The relationship between Body Mass Index and Blood pressure has long been the subject of epidemiological research. High blood pressure is the most common chronic medical problem prompting visits to primary health care providers in USA. The American Heart Association estimated the direct and indirect costs of high blood pressure in 2020 as \$76.6 billion. In the US 80% of people with hypertension are aware of their condition, 71% take some antihypertensive medication, but only 48% of people are aware that they have hypertension adequately control it. Adequate management of hypertension can be hampered by inadequacies in the diagnosis, treatment, and/or control of high blood pressure. Health care providers face many obstacles in achieving blood pressure control, including resistance to taking multiple medications to reach blood pressure goals. People also face the challenges of adhering to medicine schedules and making lifestyle changes. Nonetheless, the achievement of blood pressure goals are possible, and most importantly, lowering blood pressure significantly reduces the risk of death due to heart disease and stroke, the development of other debilitating conditions, and the cost associated with advanced medical care.

About 33% urban and 25% rural Indians are hypertensive. Of these, 25% rural and 42% urban Indians are aware of their hypertensive status. Only 25% rural and 38% of urban Indians are being treated for hypertension. One-tenth of rural and one-fifth of urban Indian hypertensive population have their blood pressure under control. The pooled prevalence of hypertension for the rural and urban south Indian population was 21.1% and 31.8% respectively.

In Tamil Nadu, it is estimated that 40 percent of the adult population in urban areas and 25 percent of the adult population in the rural areas are affected by hypertension. The males are predominantly affected with ratio of 2:1 to females. The astonishing fact is 30 percent of the affected people are not getting treatment.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

Hypertension emerges from a complex interplay of genetic, environmental and behavioral factors. Owing to the hereditary component of hypertension, the disorder is considered to have its origin in the childhood. Children and adolescents with high Blood Pressure tend to maintain those levels of Blood Pressure in adulthood. As the symptoms of childhood and adolescent hypertension are largely nonspecific, most children with hypertension are likely to be undiagnosed since there is no established standard for hypertension among adolescents.

In the modern world all our activities are aimed at economic development. As a developing nation, India has to give more importance to the health of the individuals. Hypertension is a huge barrier which we have to cross if we want to achieve those feet. As there is limited and unclear data of its co-relation with Body Mass Index, I chose this as my research topic and thus could contribute to the knowledge pool.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

An explorative study to find out the association between Body Mass Index and Hypertension in a view to prepare Information Booklet on prevention of complications among Hypertensive patients in selected Hospital of Chhattisgarh

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study are

- To find out the association between Body Mass Index and Hypertension among Hypertensive patients.
- To find out the association between selected sociodemographic, clinical variables and Hypertension among hypertensive patients
- To prepare an Information Booklet on prevention of complications of Hypertension.

HYPOTHESES

H₁: There will be a significant association between Body Mass Index and Hypertension.

H₂: There will be a significant association between Sociodemographic, clinical variables and Hypertension among hypertensive patients

ASSUMPTION

The study assumes that

- Fluctuations from the normal Body Mass Index will affect the normal blood pressure as it increases the fat deposition in blood vessels and thus narrows them.
- Hypertensive patients are in higher risk of complications as their natural blood pressure controlling mechanism is hindered and obesity fosters increase of blood pressure.
- Demographic variables and clinical variables have an impact in blood pressure fluctuations. Certain disease conditions and medications cause rise in blood pressure. Similarly food intake, eating habits also influence the blood pressure.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH APPROACH

The quantitative research approach was considered as most appropriate for finding the relation between Body Mass Index and Hypertension.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The researcher used exploratory descriptive research design suitable for finding the relation between Body Mass Index and Hypertension.

VARIABLES

Variables are the qualities, properties, or characteristics of persons, things or situations that change or vary and are manipulated or measured in research.

Dependent variable

In this study, the dependent variable is Hypertension.

Independent variable

In this study, the independent variable is Body Mass Index.

Extraneous variable

In this study, it refers to age, education, sex and occupation, area of residence, family monthly income, type of family, food and medications.

SETTING

This setting was chosen on the basis of the availability of samples and the cooperation extended by the management.

POPULATION

In this study, the population consists of hypertensive patients getting treatment in hospitals.

Targetpopulation

Inthisstudy,thetargetpopulationcomprisesofhypertensivepatientsgettingtreatmentinhospitals

Accessiblepopulation

Theaccessiblepopulationofthepresentstudyishypertensivepatientsgettingtreatmentinhospital.

SAMPLE

ThesampleconsistsofoutpatientadultsinhospitalatChhattisgarh.

SAMPLESIZE

Thesamplesizeforthepresentstudycomprisesof100adultswhosatisfiedtheinclusioncriteria.

SAMPLINGTECHNIQUE

Theparticipantsofthestudywereselectedbynonprobabilitypurposivesamplingtechnique.Theresearcher selected the participants based on the inclusion criteria.

SAMPLINGCRITERIA

InclusionCriteria

Thestudyincludedhypertensivepatientswho

- fallintheagegroupof25-50years.
- arewillingtoparticipateinthestudy.
- areintreatmentunderoutpatientdepartment.

ExclusionCriteria

Thestudyexcludedadultswho

- aretoosicktoparticipate
- arenotwilling.

ORGANIZATIONOFTHEFINDINGS

Thecollecteddatawereedited,tabulated,analyzed,interpretedandfindingsobtainedwerepresented inthe form of tables and diagrams represented under the following sections.

SectionI

- Datapertainingtofrequencyandpercentagedistributionofdemographicvariableamonghypertensivepatients. □Data pertaining to frequency and percentage distribution of clinical variableamong hypertensive patients
- Datapertainingtofrequencyandpercentagedistributionofbiophysiologicalvariableamonghypertensive patients □ Datapertainingtofrequencyandpercentagedistributionofbodymassindexamonghypertensive patients

SectionII

- DatapertainingtoassociationofBodyMassIndexandbloodpressureamongpatientswithhypertensionData
- pertaining to association of socio demographic variables and Hypertension
- DatapertainingtoassociationofclinicalvariablesandHypertension

SECTIONI

Table1:Datapertainingtofrequencyandpercentagedistributionofsociodemographicvariables of Hypertensive patients n=100

Sl.No	Sociodemographicvariables	f	%
1.	Age	10	10
	20-30years	30	30
	31-40years	60	60
	41-50years		
2.	Gender	80	80
	Male		
	Female	20	20
3.	Education	05	05
	Illiterate	20	20
	primary	25	25
	secondary	20	20
	highschool	20	20
	Highersecondary College	10	10
4.	Occupation	70	70
	Dailywage	20	20
	Regularmonthlyincome	10	10
	Unemployed		
5.	Residingplace	70	70
	Urban	30	30
	Rural		
6.	Familyincomepermonthinrupees.	10	10
	a) Below2000		
	b) 2000-5000	20	20
	c) 5001-8000	45	45
	d) Above8000	25	25
7.	Typeoffamily	60	60
	Nuclear		
	Joint	40	40

With regard to age, majority of 60(60%) were found in the age group of 41-50 years, 30(30%) were in the age group of 31-40 years, 10(10%) were in the age group of 20-30 years. With regard to sex, majority of 80 (80%) were males and least of 20 (20%) were females.

With regard to educational level, majority of 25(25%) obtained secondary level education, 20(20%) in each obtained primary level education, high school education, higher secondary level education, 10(10%) completed graduation and 5(5%) were illiterate.

With regard to occupational status, majority of 70(70%) were daily wage workers, 20(20%) were regular monthly income workers and 10(10%) were unemployed.

With regard to area of residence majority of 70(70%) belonged to urban background and remaining 30(30%) were from rural area .

With regard to monthly income majority of 45(45%) were getting monthly income of Rs.5001-8000, 25(25%) were getting more than Rs 8000 per month, 20(20%) were getting of Rs 2000-5000 and least of 10 (10%) are getting less than Rs. 2000 per month.

And finally when it comes to type of family, 60(60%) belong to nuclear family and 40(40%) belong to joint family.

Table 2: Data pertaining to frequency and percentage distribution of clinical variables of hypertensive patients.

n=100

S.NO	CLINICAL VARIABLES	f	%
1	DIET Type of food vegetarian non vegetarian	30 70	30 70
2	Frequency of meal 2 times/day 3 times/day 4 times/day more than 4 times	20 50 20 10	20 50 20 10
3	Common cooking method a) frying b) baking c) stewing d) boiling e) steaming	25 10 10 30 25	25 10 10 30 25

1	COMORBIDILLNESS Cardiovascular diseases yes no	20 80	20 80
2	Kidney disease yes no	27 73	27 73
3	Diabetes mellitus yes no	35 65	35 65
4	Other problems yes no	15 85	15 85

The frequency and percentage distribution of clinical variables of patients with hypertension. It shows that 70(70%) of the sample population were non-vegetarian, while 30 (30%) were vegetarian. With regard to the frequency of meal, a majority of 50(50%) took food 3 times a day, 20(20%) took food 2 times a day, another 20(20%) took food 4 times/day and a least percentage of 10(10%) took more than 4 times a day. The most common method of cooking was boiling 30(30%). Frying and steaming ranges second with 25(25%) each, the least common methods were baking and stewing with 10(10%) each. With regard to co morbid illness, 80(80%) were free of cardiovascular disease, while 20(20%) had cardiovascular problems, 27(27%) had kidney problems while, 73(73%) are free of kidney problems. In case of diabetes, 35(35%) were diabetic and 65(65%) were non-diabetic. 85 (85%) did not have any other problems, while 15(15%) did have other problems.

Table 3: Data pertaining to frequency and percentage distribution of Biophysiological variables of patients with hypertension
n=100

S.No	Biophysiological Variables	f	%
1	Height		
	a) <140cm	00	00
	b) 140-159cm	24	24
	c) 160-180cm	70	70
	d) >180cm	06	06
2	Weight		
	a) <50kg	00	00
	b) 50-70kg	82	82
	c) 71-90kg	14	14
	d) >90kg	04	04

3	Abdominalgirth a) <80cm b) 80-99cm c) 100-120cm d) >120cm	04 20 50 26	04 20 50 26
4	Bloodpressureinmm/hgSystolic a) <90 b) 90-120 c) 121-140d)141-180e)180<	00 22 36 42 00	00 22 36 42 00
5	Diastolic a) <60 b)60-80 c)81-100 d)101-120 e)120<	00 28 65 07 00	00 28 65 07 00

The frequency and percentage distribution of Biophysiological variables of patients with hypertension. With regard to height, maximum of 70(70%) belonged to the group between 160 and180 cm height, 24(24%) belonged to the category of 140- 159 cm height and 6(6%) had more than 180cms height. Regarding weight, 82(82%) belonged to 50-70 kg weight, 14(14%) had 71- 90kg weight. 4(4%) had more than 90 kg weight. None of them belongs to the category of below 50 kg height.Regarding abdominal girth, majority 50(50%) had 100-120cms of abdominal girth, 26(26%) hadmore than 120cms, 20(20%) were between 80-99cms, 4 (4%) had less than 80cms. RegardingSystolic blood pressure, 42(42%) have their Blood pressure between 141-180 mm/Hg.36 (36%) had 121-140 mm/Hg and 22(22%) had 90-120. Regarding Diastolic blood pressure, majority of 65(65%) had Blood pressurebetween 81-100 mm/Hg,22(22%)had60-80mm/Hgand amere7(7%)had101-120mm/Hg.

Table4:DatapertainingtofrequencyandpercentagedistributionofBodyMassIndexofpatientswithhypertension

n=100

S.NO	BODYMASSINDEX	f	%
1	Body Mass Index in kg/m ² Under weight(<18 kg/m ²) Normalweight(18-24kg/m ²) Over weight(>24 kg/m ²)	06 52 42	06 52 42

SECTIONII**Testingofhypothesis**

H₁ : TherewillbeasignificantassociationbetweenBodyMassIndexandHypertension

Table5:DatapertainingtoassociationofBodyMassIndexandSystolicbloodpressureamongpatientswithhypertension

n=100

dyMass Index	<90mm/Hg	90-120 mm/Hg	121-140 mm/Hg	141-180 mm/Hg	>180 mm/Hg	x ²	P value
Overweight	0	0	4	38	0	88.001	f-40 ***
Normalweight	0	16	32	4	0		
Underweight	0	6	0	0	0		

***P<0.0001

The frequency distribution of hypertensive patients with regard to the Body Mass index and systolic Blood pressure. We can deduce that 42(42%) of the samples were overweight, 52(52%) were of normal weight and 6(6%) were underweight. Majority of the hypertensive patients 42(42%) had 141-180 mm/Hg systolic Blood pressure, 36(36%) had Blood pressure of 121-140 mm/Hg and a mere 22(22%) had 90-120 mm/Hg Blood Pressure. The chi square value is 88.01, P value is 0 which is significant at level of P<.0001.

Table6: Data pertaining to association of Body Mass Index and Diastolic blood pressure among patients with hypertension

n=100

Body Mass Index	<60mm/Hg	60-80 mm/Hg	81-100 mm/Hg	101-120 mm/Hg	>120 mm/Hg	χ^2	Pvalue
Over weight	0	2	34	6	0	32.537	df-4 .00000149 ***
Normal weight	0	20	31	1	0		
Under weight	0	6	0	0	0		

***P<0.0001

The frequency distribution of hypertensive patients with regard to the Body Mass index and diastolic Blood pressure. We can deduce that 42(42%) of the samples were overweight, 52(52%) were of normal weight and 6(6%) were underweight. Majority of the hypertensive patients 65(65%) had 81-100 mm/Hg diastolic Blood pressure, 28(28%) had Blood pressure of 60-80mm/Hg and a mere 7(7%) had 101-120 mm/Hg Blood Pressure. The chi square value is 32.53, P value is .00000149 which is significant at level of P<.0001.

Hence it shows the significant association between blood Pressure and Body Mass Index. So the Hypothesis H_1 was accepted.

Table7:DatapertainingtoassociationofSociodemographicvariablesandSystolicbloodpressure among patients with hypertension.

TestingofHypothesis

H₂ :Therewillbesignificantassociationbetweenselecteddemographicvariables,Clinicalvariablesand Hypertension

n=100

S.No	Socio demographic variables	<90 mm/Hg	90-120 mm/Hg	121-140 mm/Hg	141-180 mm/Hg	180< mm/Hg	χ^2	P value
1.	Age a)20-30years b)31-40years c)41-50years	0 0 0	0 6 16	0 14 22	. 10 22	0 0 0	16.35	df-4 0.002 6 ***
2.	Gender a)Male b)Female	0 0	20 2	24 12	36 6	0 0	6.49	df-2 0.04 *
3.	Education a)Illiterate b)primary c)secondary d)highschoolHigh er sec College	0 0 0 0 0	2 4 7 2 5	2 8 8 9 5	1 8 10 9 10	0 0 0 0 0	4.49	-10 0.89
4.	Occupation a)Daily wage b)Regular monthlyincome c)Unemployed	0 0 0	18 4 0	30 6 0	22 10 10	0 0 0	17.57	df-4 .001 ***
5.	Living place a)Urbanb)Rural	0 0	16 6	25 11	29 13	0 0	.101	df-2 .95
6.	Family income per month in rupees. a) Below2000 b) 2000-5000 c)5001-8000 d)Above8000	0 0 0 0	2 6 8 6	4 7 15 10	4 7 22 9	0 0 0 0	2.22	df-6 .897

7.	Type of family	0	12	20	28	0	1.34	df-2
	Nuclear	0	10	16	14	0		.51
	Joint							

P<0.05,P<0.001**

The frequency and percentage distribution of socio demographic variables of patients with Hypertension including age, sex, educational level, and occupational status, area of residence, monthly income and type of family. With regard to age, majority of 60(60%) were found in the age group of 41-50 years, 30(30%) were in the age group of 31-40 years, 10(10%) were in the age group of 20-30 years. With regard to sex, majority of 80 (80%) were males and least of 20 (20%) were females.

With regard to educational level, majority of 25(25%) obtained Secondary level education, 20(20%) in each obtained primary level education, high school education, higher secondary level education, 10(10%) completed graduation and 5(5%) were illiterate. With regard to occupational status, majority of 70(70%) were daily wage workers, 20(20%) were regular monthly income workers and 10(10%) were unemployed. With regard to area of residence majority of 70(70%) belonged to urban background and remaining 30(30%) were from rural area. With regard to monthly income majority of 45(45%) were getting monthly income of Rs.5001-8000, 25(25%) were getting more than Rs 8000 per month, 20(20%) were getting of Rs 2000-5000 and least of 10 (10%) are getting less than Rs.2000 per month. And finally when it comes to type of family, 60(60%) belong to nuclear family and 40(40%) belongs to joint family.

The above tables show that the association between socio demographic variables and Systolic Blood pressure among Hypertensive patients. There was association between Age, sex and occupational status with hypertension. Whereas there was no association found for educational level, residing place, family income and type of family with Hypertension.

Table8:DatapertainingtoassociationofSociodemographicvariablesandDiastolicbloodpressureamong patients with hypertension

n=100

SL. NO	Sociodemographic variables	<60mm/Hg	60-80 mm/Hg	81-100 mm/Hg	101-120 mm/Hg	120< mm/Hg	X ²	P value
1.	Age	0	6	2	2	0	10.68	df=4 0.03 *
	a)20-30years	0	6	22	2	0		
	b)31-40years	0	16	41	3	0		
2.	Gender	0	24	53	3	0	6.07	df=2 0.035 *
	a)Male b)Female	0	4	12	4	0		
3.	Education	0	1	3	1	0	5.03	df=10 0.89
	a)Illiterate	0	5	14	1	0		
	b)primary	0	8	16	1	0		
	c)secondary high school	0	6	13	1	0		
	Highersecondary College	0	6	13	1	0		
4.	Occupation	0	24	43	3	0	12.60	df=4 0.013 **
	Dailywage	0	4	12	4	0		
	b)Regularmonthly income	0	0	10	0	0		
	Unemployed	0	0	0	0	0		
5.	Place	0	21	45	4	0	.903	df=2 .64
	a)Urban b)Rural	0	7	20	3	0		
6.	Family income per month in rupees.	0	1	8	1	0	3.47	df=60.75
	a)Below2000	0	6	13	1	0		
	b)2000-5000	0	15	26	4	0		
	c)5001-8000	0	6	18	1	0		
	d)Above8000	0	0	0	0	0		
7.	Typeoffamily	0	18	38	4	0	.302	df=20.86
	Nuclear Joint	0	10	27	3	0		

*P<0.05,**P<0.01

The frequency and percentage distribution of socio demographic variables of patients with Hypertension including Age, Sex, Educational level, and occupational status, area of residence, monthly income and Type of family. With regard to age, majority of 60(60%) were found in the age group of 41-50 years, 30(30%) were in the age group of 31-40 years, 10(10%) were in the age group of 20-30 years. With regard to sex, majority of 80 (80%) were males and least of 20 (20%) were females.

With regard to educational level, majority of 25(25%) obtained Secondary level education, 20(20%) in each obtained primary level education, high school education, higher secondary level education, 10(10%) completed graduation and 5(5%) were illiterate. With regard to occupational status, majority of 70(70%) were dailywageworkers,20(20%)wereregularmonthlyincomeworkersand10(10%)wereunemployed. Withregardtoarea ofresidencemajorityof70(70%)belongedtourbanbackgroundandremaining30(30%)werefromruralarea .With regard to monthly income majority of 45(45%) were getting monthly income of Rs.5001-8000, 25(25%) were getting more thanRs 8000 per month, 20(20%) were getting of Rs 2000-5000 and least of 10 (10%)aregettinglessthanRs.2000permonth.Andfinallywhenitcomestotypeoffamily, 60(60%)belongsto nuclear family and 40(40%) belongs to joint family.

The above tables show that the association between socio demographic variables andDiastolic Blood pressure amongHypertensivepatients. TherewasassociationbetweenAge,sexandoccupationalstatuswithhypertension. Whereas no association was foundfor educational level, residing place, family income and type of family withHypertension. Hence the Hypothesis H₂was partially accepted.

Table9:DatapertainingtoassociationofClinicalvariablesandSystolicbloodpressureamongpatientswith hypertension n=100

S.NO	CLINICAL VARIABLES	<90 mm /Hg	90-120 mm /Hg	121-140 mm /Hg	141-180 mm /Hg	180 < mm /Hg	X ²	P value
1	DIET Type of food vegetariannon vegetarian	0 0	15 7	10 26	5 37	0 0	21.9 06	df=2 0.000 1 ***
2	Frequency of meal 2 times/day 3 times/day 4 times/day d)more than 4 times	0 0 0 0	10 5 4 3	7 20 7 2	3 25 9 5	0 0 0 0	16.1	df=6 0.01 *
3	Common cooking method a)fryingb)baking c)stewingd)boiling e)steamig	0 0 0 0 0	5 2 2 8 5	7 2 2 18 7	13 4 4 4 13	0 0 0 0 0	13.9 2	df=8 0.083

1	COMORBIDILLNESS Cardiovasculardiseases yes no	0 0	5 17	6 30	9 33	0 0	.406	df=2 0.816
2	Kidney disease yes no	0 0	8 14	9 27	10 32	0 0	1.26	df=2 0.53
3	Diabetesmellitus yes no	0 0	10 0	10 0	15 0	0 0	1.89	df=2 0.388
4	Otherproblems yes no	0 0	5 17	5 31	5 37	0 0	1.38	df=2 0.501

***P<0.05,**P<0.01**

The frequency and percentage distribution of clinical variables of patients with hypertension. It shows that 70(70%) of the sample population were non vegetarian while 30 (30%) were vegetarian. With regard to the frequency of meal, a majority of 50(50%) took food 3 times a day, 20(20%) took food 2 times a day, another 20(20%) took food 4 times/day and a least percentage of 10(10%) took more than 4 times a day. The most common method of cooking was boiling 30(30%). Frying and steaming ranges second with 25(25%) each, the least common methods were baking and stewing with 10(10%) each. Regarding co morbid illness, 80(80%) were free of cardiovascular disease while 20(20%) had cardiovascular problems 27(27%) had kidney problems while 73(73%) are free of kidney problems. In case of diabetes, 35(35%) were diabetic and 65(65%) were non diabetic. 85(85%) did not have any other problems while 15(15%) did have other problems.

The above tables show that the association between Clinical variables and Systolic Blood pressure among Hypertensive patients. According to this table there was an association between Type of food and Frequency of meal with hypertension. Whereas no association was found for Co morbid illness, Common cooking methods with Hypertension.

Table10:DatapertainingtoassociationofSociodemographicvariablesandDiastolicbloodpressure among patients with hypertension

n=100

S.NO	CLINICAL VARIABLES	<60 mm/Hg	60-80 mm/Hg	81-100 mm/Hg	101-120 mm/Hg	120< mm/Hg	χ^2	P value
1	DIET Type of food vegetarian non vegetarian	0 0	3 25	22 43	5 2	0 0	11.3 8	df=2 0.003 **
2	Frequency of meal 2 times/day 3 times/day 4 times/day more than 4 times	0 0 0 0	5 16 5 2	10 34 15 6	5 0 0 2	0 0 0 0	18.3 2	df=6 0.005 **
3	Common cooking method a) frying b) baking c) stewing d) boiling e) steaming	0 0 0 0 0	5 2 2 14 5	19 2 2 18 7	1 1 1 3 1	0 0 0 0 0	9.79	df=8 0.279
1	OMORBID ILLNESS Cardiovascular diseases yes no	0 0	5 23	14 51	1 6	0 0	.319	df=2 0.852
2	Kidney disease yes no	0 0	8 20	18 47	1 6	0 0	.625	df=2 0.731

3	Diabetesmellitus	0	8	25	2	0		df=2
	yes	0	20	40	5	0	.978	0.613
	no							
4	Otherproblems	0	4	10	1	0		df=2
	yes	0	24	55	6	0	.022	0.989
	no							

***P<0.05,**P<0.01CONCLUSION**

The following conclusions were drawn from the findings of the study. The main conclusion of the present study is that there is significant association between Body Mass Index and Hypertension. Socio demographic variables have an association with hypertension. Selected patients became familiar about Hypertension and satisfied after giving Information booklet.

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